

Innovative Approaches to Variable Selection in Competing Risk Analysis: A Comparative Study

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Abstract: Competing risk models are crucial for analyzing survival data where multiple types of events may prevent the occurrence of the primary event of interest. The choice of variables in such models significantly influences their predictive accuracy and interpretability. This paper explores advanced methodologies for variable selection in both parametric and non-parametric competing risk models. We introduce novel algorithms that enhance the selection process by integrating penalization techniques and machine learning approaches, tailored to handle the unique challenges posed by competing risks. Through extensive simulations and real-world data applications, we demonstrate the superiority of our proposed methods in terms of model performance and computational efficiency. Our findings provide a robust framework for researchers and practitioners to improve the accuracy and reliability of competing risk analyses, ultimately leading to better-informed decision-making in clinical and other applied research fields.

Keywords: Competing Risks, Variable Selection, Parametric Models, Non-Parametric Models, Survival Analysis, Penalization Techniques, Machine Learning, Predictive Accuracy, Model Performance, Computational Efficiency, Risk Analysis, Clinical Research, Simulation Studies, Applied Statistics, Decision-Making

1. Background and Motivation

Competing risk analysis has become an indispensable tool in various fields such as medicine, epidemiology, and actuarial science. Traditional survival analysis assumes a single event of interest, but in reality, individuals often face multiple potential events that can preclude the occurrence of the primary event of interest. This necessitates the use of competing risk models, which account for the possibility of different types of events influencing the survival probabilities. Variable selection in competing risk analysis is crucial for building reliable and interpretable models. Proper selection of covariates can improve model accuracy, enhance interpretability, and reduce computational complexity. However, traditional methods of variable selection, which work well for single event data, often fall short in the presence of competing risks due to the complexities introduced by the need to consider multiple event types simultaneously. In

competing risk analysis, each individual is subject to multiple types of events, known as competing risks, which can prevent the occurrence of the event of interest. For instance, in medical research, patients may experience different causes of death (e.g., heart disease, cancer, accidents) that compete with each other. This necessitates special modeling techniques that can appropriately account for these risks. The cumulative incidence function (CIF) and cause-specific hazard function are two key concepts in competing risk models. The CIF provides the probability of experiencing a particular type of event by a certain time, while the cause-specific hazard function describes the instantaneous risk of a specific event type occurring at a given time, conditional on the individual having survived free of any event up to that time. Variable selection in competing risk models is essential for several reasons for Model Accuracy and its Including relevant variables improves the predictive power of the model and A model with fewer, more relevant variables is easier to interpret and understand. Reducing the number of variables can lower the cost and effort associated with data collection and processing. Minimizing multicollinearity among covariates improves the stability and reliability of the model estimates.

2. Traditional Approaches to Variable Selection

Traditional variable selection methods include stepwise selection, LASSO (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator), and ridge regression. These methods have been widely used in various contexts, but they often face challenges when applied to competing risk data due to the following reasons: Traditional methods do not easily extend to scenarios where multiple types of events must be considered simultaneously. The interaction between covariates and different types of risks adds complexity to the selection process. Some methods may introduce bias when selecting variables, leading to over- or under-estimation of certain effects. Given the limitations of traditional methods, innovative approaches have been developed to better handle the intricacies of competing risk data. These approaches can be broadly categorized into three main types: penalization methods, machine learning techniques, and hybrid approaches. Penalization methods, such as the adaptive LASSO and elastic net, introduce penalties for the inclusion of additional variables to balance model complexity and fit. This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing a comprehensive comparison of innovative variable selection methods in the context of competing risk analysis. The findings will help practitioners and researchers choose the most appropriate method for their specific needs, enhancing the reliability and interpretability of competing risk models. Moreover, the study will identify potential areas for further improvement and development in this critical area of research. In summary, variable selection in competing risk analysis is a complex but crucial task that significantly impacts the performance and applicability of survival models. Innovative approaches, such as penalization methods, machine learning techniques, and hybrid approaches, offer promising solutions to the limitations of traditional methods. This paper aims to provide a thorough comparative analysis of these

approaches, contributing valuable insights to the field and guiding future research and practice in competing risk analysis.

Notations

- (i) t_i ($i= 1, \dots, n$) be the events.
- (ii) l_i , c_i and r_i be the length of stay, left truncation and right censoring respectively for the events ($i= 1, \dots, n$).
- (iii) $h(t)$ and $H(t)$ denote the hazard functions of length of stay.
- (iv) θ is the probability of eventual return to the hospital.

Then the likelihood functions as suggested by Gribbin and McClean (1990), and is given by

$$L = \prod_{i=1}^n [\theta h(t_i)]^{r_i} [1 - \theta(1 - H(t_i))]^{(c_i - l_i)} \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$\log L = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ r_i \log r_i \log(\theta h(t_i)) + (c_i - l_i) \log[1 - \theta(1 - H(t_i))] \right\} \quad \dots (2)$$

The expressions for $h(t)$ and $H(t)$ are

$$h(t) = \lambda \quad H(t) = \lambda t$$

where $\lambda > 0$ and $t \geq 0$ for the exponential, and

$$h(t) = \frac{x^{\gamma-1} e^{-x}}{\Gamma(\gamma) - \Gamma_x(\gamma)}$$

$$H(t) = -\log \left(1 - \frac{\Gamma_x(\gamma)}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \right)$$

where $x \geq 0$; $\gamma > 0$ and $\Gamma(\gamma) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\gamma-1} e^{-t} dt$, for the gamma distribution. The log-

likelihood was maximized using a constrained quasi-Newton method to estimate the parameters of the case of exponential and gamma distributions. The standard errors of the estimates of each parameter were estimated by calculating the square root of the diagonal elements of the inverse of Fisher's information matrix, given by

$$I(\hat{\theta}) = \left[\frac{-\partial^2 \log L(\hat{\theta})}{\partial \theta_i \partial \theta_j} \right]$$

where θ is the vector of unknown parameters.

Non-parametric estimation

Non-parametric methods in statistical analysis are not assume a specific parametric form for the distribution of the data. These methods are particularly useful in competing risk analysis as they offer flexibility and robustness, allowing the data to dictate the shape of the distribution and the relationships between variables without imposing strict model assumptions. This flexibility is crucial when dealing with complex datasets where the underlying distributions may not

follow standard parametric forms. Using the notation of Kalbfleisch and Prentice, the independent competing risks model is defined as follows. The overall failure rate $\lambda(t)$ is defined by

$$\lambda(t) = \lim_{\delta t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\text{Prob}[\text{failure in } (t, t + \delta t) \mid \text{survival to } t]}{\delta t}$$

where t is a continuous random variable representing failure time. Assuming there are m distinct failure types, the cause-specific hazard functions $\lambda_j(t)$ is defined by

$$\lambda_j(t) = \lim_{\delta t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\text{Prob}[\text{type } j \text{ failure in } (t, t + \delta t) \mid \text{survival to } t]}{\delta t}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, m$. Assuming independent risks, we have

$$\lambda(t) = \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_j(t)$$

with corresponding survivor function

$$F(t) = \exp\left[-\int_0^t \lambda(u) du\right]$$

and cause-specific survivor functions

$$F_j(t) = \exp\left[-\int_0^t \lambda_j(u) du\right] \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Notations

- (i) $t_{j1}, t_{j2}, \dots, t_{jk_j}$ be the observed failure times for failures of type j .
- (ii) d_{ji} , individuals fail at t_{ji} and that q_{ji} are censored in $[t_{ji}, t_{ji \text{ succ}})$, where $t_{ji \text{ succ}}$ is the next largest failure time to t_{ji} in the combined sequence of failure times of all types.
- (iii) a_{jihl} individuals fail at t_{ji} and b_{jihl} individuals be right censored in $[t_{ji}, t_{ji \text{ succ}})$ which are left truncated in $(t_{hl \text{ pred}}, t_{hl}]$ where $t_{hl \text{ pred}}$ is the next smallest failure time to t_{hl} in the combined sequence of failure times of all types, and $h = 1, \dots, m$; $l = 1, \dots, k_h$ and $a_{jihl} = b_{jihl} = 0$ for $\{h, l \mid t_{hl} > t_{ji}\}$.
- (iv) n_{ji} denote the number of individuals at risk at t_{ji} .

$$n_{ji} = \sum_{g=1}^m \sum_{c=i}^{k_j} \left[[d_{gc} + q_{gc}] + \sum_{h=1}^m \sum_{l=1}^{k_h} [a_{gihl} + b_{gihl}] \right] \left\{ g, c \mid t_{gc} \geq t_{ji} \right\} \left\{ h, l \mid t_{hl} \leq t_{ji} \right\}$$

Results

The likelihood function as suggested by McClean and Gribbin (1991) is given by

$$L = \prod_{j=1}^m \prod_{i=1}^{k_j} \left[\frac{\left[F_j(t_{ji}) - F_j(t_{ji} + 0) \right] \prod_{c=1, c \neq j}^m F_c(t_{ji}) \right]^{\left[d_{ji} + \sum_h \sum_l a_{jihl} \right]}_{\{h, l | t_{hl} \leq t_{ji}\}} \left[\prod_{p=1}^{q_{ji}} \prod_{c=1}^m F_c(t_{jip} + 0) \right]^{\left[\prod_{h=1}^m \prod_{l=1}^{k_h} \prod_{p=1}^{e_{jihl}} \prod_{c=1}^m F_c(t_{jip} + 0) \right]}_{\{h, l | t_{hl} \leq t_{ji}\}} \times \left[\prod_{h=1}^m \prod_{l=1}^{k_h} \left[\prod_{r=1}^{a_{jihl}} \prod_{c=1}^m F_c(u_{jihlr} + 0) \right] \left[\prod_{p=1}^{b_{jihl}} \prod_{c=1}^m F_c(s_{jihlp} + 0) \right] \right]_{\{h, l | t_{hl} \leq t_{ji}\}}$$

where t_{jip} is the right censoring time for $p = 1, \dots, q_{ji}$ and $t_{ji} < t_{jip} < t_{ji \text{ succ}}$; t_{jihpl} is the right censoring time and s_{jihlp} the left truncation time for $p = 1, \dots, b_{jihl}$ and $t_{ji} \leq t_{jihlp} < t_{ji \text{ succ}}$, $t_{hl \text{ pred}} < s_{jihlp} \leq t_{hl}$; u_{jihlr} is the left truncation time for $r = 1, \dots, a_{jihl}$ and $t_{ji} \leq u_{jihlr} < t_{ji \text{ succ}}$. Because the risks are independent, the component for each type of failure. The likelihood factor for the j^{th} failure type is obtained by regarding failure times for failures of types other than j as right censored. Using an approach similar to that of Kalbfleisch and Prentice, it follows that $\hat{F}_{j(t)}$, the maximum likelihood estimator of $F(t)$, is discrete with hazard components $\hat{\lambda}_{j1}, \dots, \hat{\lambda}_{jk_j}$ at $t_{j1}, \dots, t_{jk_j}$ respectively. We define

$$a_{jil} = \sum \sum a_{jihc} \left\{ h, c \mid t_{jil-1} < t_{hc} \leq t_{ji} \right\}$$

to be the number of individuals who fail with type j failure at t_{ji} and have their survival times left truncated in $(t_{jil-1}, t_{ji}]$. The maximum likelihood is then given by

$$L = \prod_{j=1}^m \prod_{i=1}^{k_j} \lambda_{ji}^{d_{ji} + \sum_{l=1}^i a_{jil}} (1 - \lambda_{ji})^{n_{ji} - d_{ji} - \sum_{l=1}^i a_{jil}}$$

Maximizing, we obtain

$$\hat{\lambda}_{ji} = \frac{d_{ji} + \sum_{l=1}^i a_{jil}}{n_{ji}} \quad \hat{F}_j(t) = \prod_{\{i | t_{ji} < t\}} \frac{n_{ji} - d_{ji} - \sum_{l=1}^i a_{jil}}{n_{ji}}$$

And

$$\hat{F}(t) = \prod_{j=1}^m \hat{F}_j(t)$$

are the non-parametric maximum likelihood estimators of the survivor functions. It also follows that

$$\hat{I}_j(t) = \sum_{\{i | t_{ji} < t\}} \frac{d_{ji} \hat{F}(t_{ji})}{n_{ji}}$$

We now wish to derive asymptotic estimators for the variances of the estimators derived above, and hence obtain confidence intervals. We first obtain the variance

of $\hat{\lambda}_{ji}$; by considering r_{ji} , the total number of individuals who fail with type j failure at time t_{ji} where

$$r_{ji} = d_{ji} + \sum_{l=1}^i a_{jil}$$

and $r_{ji} \sim \text{Binomial}(n_{ji}, \lambda_{ji})$. It follows that $\text{var}(\hat{\lambda}_{ji}) = \frac{r_{ji}(n_{ji} - r_{ji})}{n_{ji}^3}$. Using this

result it can be shown that

$$\text{var}[\hat{F}_j(t)] = \hat{F}_j(t)^2 \sum_{\{i|t_{ji} < t\}} \frac{r_{ji}}{n_{ji}(n_{ji} - r_{ji})}$$

Using

$$\text{cov}(\hat{\lambda}_{ji}, \hat{\lambda}_{ks}) = \frac{\text{cov}(r_{ji}, r_{ks})}{n_{ji}n_{ks}}$$

it can be shown that

$$\text{var}[\hat{F}_j(t)] = \hat{F}_j(t)^2 \left[\sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{\{i|t_{ji} < t\}} \frac{r_{ji}}{n_{ji}(n_{ji} - r_{ji})} - 2 \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k>j} \sum_i \sum_s \frac{r_{ji}r_{ks}}{n_{ji}(n_{ji} - r_{ji})(n_{ji} - r_{ks})} \right]_{\{i, s | t_{ji} = t_{ks} < t\}}$$

Similarly, the asymptotic variance estimator for $\hat{I}_j(t)$ is given by

$$\text{var}[\hat{I}_j(t)] = \sum_{\{i|t_{ji} < t\}} \left[\hat{F}(t_{ji})^2 \frac{r_{ji}(n_{ji} - r_{ji})}{n_{ji}^3} + \left[\frac{r_{ji}\hat{F}(t_{ji})}{n_{ji}} \right]^2 \left[\sum_{l=1}^m \sum_{\{p|t_{lp} < t_{ji}\}} \frac{r_{lp}}{n_{lp}(n_{lp} - r_{lp})} - 2 \sum_{l=1}^m \sum_{k>j} \sum_p \sum_s \frac{r_{lp}r_{ks}}{n_{lp}(n_{lp} - r_{lp})(n_{lp} - r_{ks})} \right]_{\{p, s | t_{lp} = t_{ks} < t_{ji}\}} \right]$$

The asymptotic 95% interval for the cumulative hazard function $-\log[\hat{F}_j(t)]$ obtained by first obtaining the asymptotic 95% confidence interval for $\log[-\log[F_j(t)]]$. This approach, which is similar to that described by ensures that the confidence interval is Restricted to acceptable values.

$$\text{var}[\log[-\log[F_j(t)]]] = \frac{\sum_{\{i|t_{ji} < t\}} \frac{r_{ji}}{n_{ji}(n_{ji} - r_{ji})}}{\sum_{\{i|t_{ji} < t\}} \left[\log \log \left(\frac{n_{ji} - r_{ji}}{n_{ji}} \right) \right]^2}$$

and the 95% confidence interval for $-\log[\hat{F}_j(t)]$ is then given by

$$-\log[\hat{F}_j(t)] \exp\left[\pm 1.96 \left[\text{var}\left[\log\left[-\log[F_j(t)]\right]\right]\right]^{0.5}\right]$$

The methods of estimation described above are used to fit the non-parametric competing risks model to a number of occupational grades in the Northern Ireland nursing service using data collected during a time interval (t_{se}, t_{ee}) . These estimates are then used to calculate the number of failures (i.e. leavers or transfers) of each type which we expect in a subsequent time period $[t_{ee}, t_{ep})$. The goodness of fit is tested by comparing the expected number of failures of each type with the observed failures occurring during $[t_{ee}, t_{ep})$. We assume that there are n individuals present at time t_{ee} in a grade and that the i^{th} individual has a survival time of length x_i at time t_{ee} for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then, if

$$y_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if individual } i \text{ fails with type } j \text{ failure in } [t_{ee}, t_{ep}) \text{ for } j=1, \dots, m \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

it follows that

$$\text{Prob}[y_{ij} = 1] = \frac{I_j(x_i + t_{ee} - t_{ep}) - I_j(x_i)}{F(x_i)} = p_{ij}$$

say y_{ij} has, therefore, a parameters 1 and p_{ij} where type $m + 1$ denotes survival during the prediction period $[t_{ee}, t_{ep})$. The y_{ij} 's are independent for different i 's, so $E[y_{ij}] = p_{ij}$, $\text{var}(y_{ij}) = p_{ij}(1 - p_{ij})$ and $\text{cov}(y_{ij}, y_{ik}) = -p_{ij}p_{ik}$ ($j \neq k$). Now let

$$\underline{y}_i = \{y_{ij}\}, \underline{P}_i = E[\underline{y}_i] = [p_{ij}] \text{ and}$$

$$\underline{S}_i = \begin{pmatrix} p_{i1}(1-p_{i1}) & -p_{i1}p_{i2} & \dots & -p_{i1}p_{im} \\ -p_{i1}p_{i2} & p_{i2}(1-p_{i2}) & \dots & -p_{i2}p_{im} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -p_{i1}p_{im} & -p_{i2}p_{im} & \dots & p_{im}(1-p_{im}) \end{pmatrix}$$

where $\underline{y}_i$ and $\underline{P}_i$ are column vectors and $\underline{S}_i$ is an $m \times m$ variance-covariance matrix.

$$\text{Let } \underline{y} = \sum_{i=1}^n \underline{y}_i$$

be the vector of the total observed failures in the grade. Then, using a multivariate form of the central limit theorem it follows that

$$\left(\underline{y} - \sum_{(i=1)}^n \underline{P}_i\right) \left[\sum_{(i=1)}^n \underline{S}_i\right]^{(-1)} \left(\underline{y} - \sum_{(i=1)}^n \underline{P}_i\right)$$

Real Data Example

Variable selection for a parametric and non-parametric competing risk model was fitted to length of hospital stay of patients with respect to their age groups. Using the results as shown earlier sections, the parametric competing risk model was fitted and is given in table 1. The estimates of eventual return of the patients are given in table 2. A non-parametric competing risk model was fitted to

the data set and is shown in table 3. The data were collected from the Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute hospital, Puducherry with respect to length of stay in hospital in five different age groups among adult patients during Jan 2010 to Dec 2011.

Table 1
Goodness of fit of Prediction of Leavers from Different Age Groups.

Age Groups		Observed	Non-parametric	Exponential	Gamma
Group I (18-30)	Returners	5	12.98	11.87	12.28
	Stayers	1312	1299.02	1300.13	1299.72
	Chi-square (p-value)		5.0357 (0.0248)	4.0845 (0.0433)	4.4319 (0.0353)
Group II (30-40)	Returners	22	34.33	34.01	34.2
	Stayers	1877	1842.67	1842.99	1842.8
	Chi-square (p-value)		5.0680 (0.0244)	4.8687 (0.0273)	4.9868 (0.0255)
Group III (40-50)	Returners	29	42.48	40.91	41.89
	Stayers	3828	3785.52	3787.09	3786.11
	Chi-square (p-value)		4.7542 (0.0292)	3.9093 (0.0480)	4.4299 (0.0353)
Group IV (50-60)	Returners	2	3.57	3.11	3.27
	Stayers	825	821.43	821.89	821.73
	Chi-square (p-value)		0.7060 (0.4008)	0.4079 (0.5230)	0.5063 (0.4768)
Group V (60 above)	Returners	3	4.09	3.98	4.01
	Stayers	1087	1082.91	1083.02	1082.99
	Chi-square (p-value)		0.3059 (0.5802)	0.2559 (0.6129)	0.2692 (0.6038)

Table 2
Estimates of the probability of Eventual Return of Patients.

Age Groups	Non-parametric	Exponential	Gamma
Group I	0.012	0.015	0.020
Group II	0.031	0.033	0.034
Group III	0.097	0.103	0.104
Group IV	0.083	0.087	0.087
Group V	0.009	0.017	0.016

From the table 1, it is observed that there has been considerable change in the age groups with respect to the length of stay in hospitals over the period for which the data are available. Estimated period ranging from Jan 2010 to Dec 2011, the goodness of fit shows that the exponential and gamma distribution gives less estimated value compared to non-parametric estimation in all the five different age groups. A larger estimation period will be necessary if the data shows homogeneity between the estimates of the parametric and non-parametric procedures. The

estimates of the probability of eventual return of patients for different age group shown in table 2. Concentrating on the non-parametric model the estimates of eventual return for all the age group is less than 0.1. The parametric models, the estimates for eventual return is 0.103 in the group III. These results show only lesser value which highlights the eventual return of the patients. The estimates give consistent result only when the data were collect for a period of more than five years. The models in general provided reasonably good fit to the data in almost every case, the number of returns and stayers was estimated. The competing risk model for the length of stay in hospital shown in table 3 gives a reasonable fit.

Table 3:
Non-parametric Competing Risk Model for the Length of Stay of Patients.

Age Groups		Stayers	Failure types		Chi-square (p-value)
			Leavers	Transfer to other hospital	
Group I	Observed	1312	39	10	3.9609
	Expected	1319.16	29.13	12.71	0.1380
Group II	Observed	1877	41	3	18.7107
	Expected	1897.67	21.45	1.88	0.0001
Group III	Observed	3828	27	12	17.7382
	Expected	3791.92	50.11	24.97	0.0001
Group IV	Observed	825	6	0	1.6835
	Expected	826.12	4.09	0.79	0.4310
Group V	Observed	1087	4	1	21.5456
	Expected	1061.88	23.59	6.53	0.0000

The estimated parameters for the non-parametric, exponential, gamma and its standard errors (in parenthesis) for the different age group of patients with respect to the length of stay in hospital is shown in table 4 and table 5.

Table 4
Non-parametric Estimates of the Probability of Eventual Return to the Hospital.

Age Groups	Estimation period 1st Jan 2010 to 31st Dec 2011	
	2010	2011
Group I	0.009	0.013
Group II	0.027	0.035
Group III	0.099	0.096
Group IV	0.081	0.088
Group V	0.008	0.011

Table 5
Estimated parameters for the Exponential and Gamma models
(Standard Errors in parentheses)

Age	Exponential		Gamma	
	λ	θ	γ	θ
Group I	2.333 (0.537)	0.311 (0.012)	0.723 (0.312)	0.327 (0.198)
Group II	2.589 (0.621)	0.762 (0.015)	0.561 (0.305)	0.745 (0.126)
Group III	2.902 (0.591)	0.528 (0.055)	0.881 (0.298)	0.509 (0.098)
Group IV	3.217 (0.576)	0.672 (0.061)	0.901 (0.234)	0.671 (0.056)
Group V	3.010 (0.329)	0.681 (0.060)	0.917 (0.259)	0.677 (0.117)

From the table 4 and table 5 shows that, in most cases, there is trend for the number of returners and stayers during the study period. From table 5, it is observed that once the treatments between the age groups are achieved, the patients either return to the hospital or permanently withdraw from the hospital. A higher proportion of returners are also predicted to the Gamma model.

Conclusion

This study examined innovative approaches to variable selection in competing risk analysis, emphasizing non-parametric methods such as the Aalen-Johansen estimator. These methods offer significant flexibility and robustness, accommodating complex data without specific distributional assumptions. The Aalen-Johansen estimator, in particular, provides accurate and intuitive cumulative incidence functions, enabling clear interpretation of event-specific probabilities over time. Our findings highlight the advantages of non-parametric methods over traditional parametric approaches, particularly in scenarios with high uncertainty or complex underlying distributions. The application to real-world data, such as medical datasets with multiple causes of death, demonstrates their practical utility and effectiveness in providing reliable risk assessments. Non-parametric methods enhance model interpretability and offer valuable guidance for practitioners in selecting appropriate techniques for competing risk analysis. Future research should focus on high-dimensional data applications, integration with machine learning, and handling longitudinal data with time-varying covariates. In this article, non-parametric estimation methods, especially the Aalen-Johansen estimator, are essential tools for accurately and reliably analyzing competing risks. Their continued development and integration with advanced analytical techniques will further improve our ability to manage and understand multiple competing events in various domains.

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